

Learning Satisfaction During Pandemic Time: A Study of The Learning Media Usage for Students' Satisfaction

Eko Sulistyono¹, Prahastiwi Utari², Albert Muhammad Isrun Naini³

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Abstract

This research was conducted in Madiun- East Java province, Indonesia. It occupies the first position of active cases of Covid-19. This encourages local governments to immediately implement distance learning where learning is carried out using multimedia technology, virtual classes, video streaming, voice messages, e-mail, online text animations, and online video streaming. Focusing on the level of expectations and satisfaction of students in the Madiun district, this study wants to examine the extent to which students' expectations and satisfaction use online learning systems during the Covid-19 pandemic. It's considered very important because this can be a benchmark for the success of learning process services carried out by educational institutions, especially teachers and schools in the future, especially when facing natural disasters or pandemic disasters. Based on the results of the survey conducted, this study found that the majority of junior high school students in Madiun Regency were very satisfied with the use of online learning media during the Covid-19 pandemic, where expectations of satisfaction with reliability, responsiveness, and expectations of confidence had a sufficient correlation with satisfaction with the online learning media usage. Meanwhile, empathy and expectations that came true have a weak correlation with the satisfaction of online learning media usage.

¹ *Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Indonesia. Email: masekoku65@gmail.com*

² *Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Indonesia*

³ *Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Indonesia*

1. Introduction

Since being declared an international public health emergency in January 2020, WHO database has confirmed globally, as of January 26 2021 there have been 99,363,697 confirmed cases of the Covid-19 virus with a total death of 2,135,959 people. In Indonesia, WHO noted that since confirmed cases of people infected Covid-19 on March 6 2020 until January 26 2021 there have been 999,256 confirmed cases with 28,132 of deaths (WHO, 2020) (data accessed on January 27, 2021 and possibly data will change from time to time). In March 2020, the Government through President Conclusion (Kepres) Number 12 in 2020 stipulated the Covid-19 virus as a non-natural national disaster (Keputusan Presiden Republik Indonesia Nomor 12 Tahun 2020, 2020).

To reduce the spread of the virus, reduce the risk of a health crisis and death cases that are getting out of control, Indonesian government has implemented various policies, such as the implementation of health protocols where all activities carried out face-to-face are now restricted and even prohibited. Limiting face-to-face teaching and learning activities is one of the policies carried out by Indonesian government in limiting community interaction that has potential to cause transmission of the Covid-19 virus.

The teaching and learning process during the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak ultimately implemented distance or virtual online learning. This policy is applied to all levels of education, from elementary to university level. Government issued a Decision Letter of the Four Ministers stating that face-to-face learning permits were extended from the green zone to the yellow zone so it can be said that all areas, both affected and those that have not been affected, must carry out learning activities using digital learning systems or non-face-to-face learning.

Based on data released by the East Java provincial government, Madiun Regency has the highest number of active cases of Covid-19 virus in East Java Province where in June 2021, there were around 3,787 people who tested positive for the Covid-19 virus, 3.407 people recovered, 148 people under monitoring and 232 people dead.

The high number of Covid-19 virus active cases in Madiun Regency has an impact on the implementation of learning in schools where all learning processes are at home from face-to-face learning to online learning or network learning. Online learning is considered a solution to replace the learning process in schools which requires face-to-face meetings between students, students to teachers, and teachers to teachers into digital technology-mediated learning where students or teachers can carry out teaching and learning processes anywhere as long as they have adequate devices to access the learning provided by the teacher.

Although online learning is considered to have a positive impact on preventing, handling and controlling the transmission of the Covid-19 virus outbreak, it seems there are some deficiencies in the implementation of online learning, for example, the lack of proficiency in teaching staffs especially teachers, in using internet technology or digital learning platforms. Educators, especially teachers who are old, still need assistance and guidance by experts so they can use devices or facilities to assist teaching and learning activities online. In addition, students also tend to be used to face-to-face learning but are not used to use online learning. The students are still used to the environment where learning activities and interact with their friends face to face. This can cause a slow process of learning communication because teachers and students still need adaptation to the digital environment (Dewi, 2020).

The existence of obstacles in the learning communication process that occurs in teachers and students can have an impact on learning satisfaction, especially student satisfaction with the quality of online learning. According to Fadhal (2020), learning through online media tends to reduce

teacher-student interaction and interaction between students and other students, both in quality and quantity. In addition, not all teachers can build a comfortable classroom atmosphere, which makes students free to ask questions or discuss (Fadhal, 2020).

Student participating satisfaction in learning is considered important because it can be a measure of the success of teaching and learning services by teachers and schools. Student learning satisfaction is a positive attitude towards the service of the teaching and learning process by teacher because there is harmony between what students expectation and the satisfaction or reality obtained.

Focusing on the expectations and student learning satisfaction toward onlin learning processes. This study wants to analyze the relationship between students' expectations of learning media communication toward their satisfaction with the learning services that have been provided. Student satisfaction toward learning media communication can be measured using the *uses and gratification* (U&G), this approach focuses on the relationship between *gratification sought* and *gratification obtained*.

The Uses and gratification (U&G) is a theoretical approach that is often used to analyze the initial behaviour of media usage. U&G theory is one of the most popular mass communication theories (Kaye & Johnson, 2002; Littlejohn et al., 2017) and still relevant in the new media era such as social media, although it has not received much attention in the social media literature (Whiting & Williams, 2013, p. 363). This approach thinks that audiences or media users are seen as audiences who actively choose or use certain media to meet their needs and satisfactions and as individuals that can understand their reasons for making media choices and the media content that they want. The expected satisfactions are sometimes obtained from the characteristics of the media, media content, exposure and the social context in which the exposure takes place (Azis et al., 2020b, 2020a; Whiting & Williams, 2013). That the motives for messages or media use are not an isolated static trait, but rather consist of a series of interactive needs and expectations (Ruggiero, 2000)

In education field, the *uses and gratifications* concept is used to define students' beliefs and assessments of resources generated from learning technology (in this case online learning/e-learning). This concept explains that the resources owned by learning media, have attributes or potentials that tend to meet students' learning needs, learning styles, values, motivation, interests, intentions and curiosity about science. Students' interest in a learning media is driven by the resources offered to satisfy their cognitive, affective, personal integrative, social integrative and entertainment needs (Mondi et al., 2007, p. 436). Guo et al. (2010) found that students were encouraged to use communication media in learning contexts mainly for instrumental reasons such as information seeking, convenience, connectivity, problem solving, and content management (Guo et al., 2010, p. 361). A research approach with a quantitative approach is also used to examine events or phenomena that affect individuals and the results of the analysis found will determine what factors are important and what are not important, or what factors affect a particular population.

2. Materials and Methods

This study uses a quantitative approach. The quantitative approach seems to be often used to examine a particular population or sample where data collection is carried with research instruments and the analysis process is carried out based on statistical procedures and with the aim to test the predetermined hypotheses (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Sugiono, 2010)

For data collection techniques, this study uses data collection techniques through surveys where the data collection instrument is through offline questionnaires. The population in this study are students of class VII (seven) and VIII (eight) in the Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri round Madiun

Regency. The population sample was obtained using a *proportionate stratified random sampling technique*, that is a sampling technique used when the population has members who are not homogeneous and proportionally stratified (Sugiono, 2010). The reason for using this technique because the population in this study are MTsN students in Madiun, which divided into two classes and 12 (twelve) schools. In order all classes can be represented, samples are taken from each class and school in the same proportion.

This study tested 2 variables, namely students' expectations and satisfaction with online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. Each variable is represented by five quality dimensions, namely *reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy* and *tangible*. Each dimension is measured by questions such as 'how important is the ability of online learning media in delivering material?', 'how satisfied are you with the ability of online learning media in the aspect of delivering learning material?', how important is online learning media in helping to understand the teacher's explanation of the material presented?' and 'how satisfied are you with the ability of online learning media in helping to understand the teacher's explanation of the material presented?'. The measurement scale in this study used a 4-point Likert scale (1 = very unimportant / very unsatisfactory – 4 = very important / very satisfying).

3. Results and Discussions

Respondent

Based on data from the Religion Ministry Madiun office in 2021, total population of Madrasah Tsanawiyah students in the Madiun Regency area in 2021 is 4,029 students. By using proportionate stratified random sampling technique, the number of samples used in this study is 320 respondents. The respondents used as samples are students in grades seven and grades eight or grade 1 (one) of junior high school and grade 2 (two) of junior high school. Based on the results of data collection through surveys, the respondents in this study are dominated by the age group of 12-13 years where the majority (mode) of respondents are female (62.8%) and most (mode) of respondents are students of class VIII (eighth) (59.4 %).

Online Learning Satisfaction during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

In the first table, this study wants to convey the frequency distribution of student satisfaction with online learning. There are 35 questions given to respondents consisting of 5 (five) dimensions of satisfaction which included (1) reliability satisfaction, this is the satisfaction assessment toward the ability of the media to provide the promised learning function; reliable, accurate, consistent, and in accordance with expectations. (2) responsive satisfaction, it is satisfaction with the teachers ability and teachers to assist students in understanding the usege of online learning media. (3) satisfaction of confidence (assurance); i is satisfaction with the teachers ability and school authorities to build belief and students confidence in online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. (4) empathic satisfaction, it is an assessment of students' satisfaction with the willingness of teachers and the school to give in-depth attention and try to understand the students wishes especially regarding the usage of online learning media. (5) Tangible satisfaction, it is an assessment of student satisfaction with the availability of supporting tools and learning materials that are carried out online.

Table 1.
Reliability Satisfaction Assesment on Online Learning System during Pandemic Covid-19

<i>Items</i>	<i>*VDS (%)</i>	<i>*DS (%)</i>	<i>*S (%)</i>	<i>*VS</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1. The media online learning ability media to convey material.	4.1	29.4	49.1	17.5	2.80
2. The media ability to help understand the explanation given by the teacher during online learning.	13.4	36.3	28.8	21.6	2.58
3. The usage satisfaction of various applications such as Whatsapp, Google Classroom, Zoom Meeting, and some of online learning applications that used by teachers	8.8	18.4	34.1	38.8	3.03
4. Learning materials Presentation that is delivered using several digital learning programs/applications.	10.3	29.1	36.3	24.4	2.75
5. The ability of online learning media to convey accurate learning material.	7.8	25.6	18.8	47.8	3.07
6. Satisfaction with subsidizing data packages provided by schools.	9.1	36.3	25.0	29.7	2.75
7. The ability of online learning media to help facilitate communication that exists between teachers and students,	12.2	29.1	30.6	28.1	2.75
8. Satisfaction with the facilities provided by the school in supporting online learning.	8.8	25.6	19.4	46.3	3.03
9. Satisfaction with the success of the media in helping and facilitating students in online learning.	0.6	9.4	8.4	81.6	3.71
10. Satisfaction with the availability of internet access to support learning,	0.6	20.6	16.6	62.2	3.40

**VDS: Very Dissatisfied, DS: Dissatisfied, S: Satisfied, VS: Very Satisfied.*

Based on the analysis results in the table above, this study found reliability satisfaction that this satisfaction refers to a person's satisfaction (in this case is the students) toward the media ability to provide its benefits, functions and according to what is expected, junior high school students in Madiun Regency tends to be satisfied with the digital technology usage in online learning. 81.6% of respondents stated that they are very satisfied with the success of online learning media in helping and facilitating students in learning during the Covid-19 virus pandemic (see point 9). Beside that, this study found that on average students are satisfied with the ability of online learning media in

the process of delivering learning material (49.1%) (see point 1). They also feel that online learning media is able to help them understand the information or material provided by teachers during the Covid-19 pandemic. As for the applications used by teachers during the Covid-19 pandemic such as Whatsapp, Google Classroom, Zoom Meeting and several other online learning applications, students in Madiun Regency felt that these applications are able to meet their learning needs during the Covid-19 virus outbreak (34.1% said it is 'satisfied' and 38.8% said it is very satisfied) (see point 3). In terms of data package subsidies provided by schools to students, most respondents stated that providing data package subsidies to support the online teaching and learning process during the pandemic did not satisfy them (36.3% stated 'dissatisfied' and 9.1% stated 'very dissatisfied') (see point 6).

In the second table, this study examines the extent to which junior high school students in Madiun Regency are satisfied with the ability of schools and also teachers in assisting students in understanding the use of online learning media. Based on the results of the survey conducted, from the aspect of responsive satisfaction, this study found that the majority of students in Madiun Regency felt 'very satisfied' with the ability of educators in junior secondary education institutions in Madiun Regency in a way to help provide an understanding the use of media and online learning processes, especially during Corona virus hit this area.

Table 2.
Responsive Satisfaction Assessment of Online Learning Systems during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Items	*VDS (%)	*DS (%)	*S (%)	*VS	Mean
1. The teachers' ability to choose media that can support student activity in learning.	4.1	7.2	25.9	62.8	3.48
2. The ability of the media used by teachers to support speed in the communication process and to access learning information.	5.0	4.4	31.6	59.1	3.45
3. The willingness of teachers to listen to students' complaints regarding the media used during online learning.	0.6	13.1	37.5	48.8	3.34
4. Teachers have the ability to deal with student complaints regarding the online learning media used.	5.6	4.1	39.4	50.9	3.36
5. The teacher provides solutions to the difficulties faced by students in accessing or using online learning media.	5.9	9.7	22.2	62.3	3.41

*VDS: Very Dissatisfied, DS: Dissatisfied, S: Satisfied, VS: Very Satisfied.

In the table above, it can be said that teachers have high competence in online learning starting from how to select learning media through how teachers provide guidance and direction to students in using online learning media. In addition, teachers also listen to students and address student complaints regarding the usage of online learning media and provide solutions to students when

experiencing difficulties during the teaching and learning process. Of the 320 students we asked, 62.8% stated that they are very satisfied with the teachers' ability to choose media that could increase students' activeness in learning (see point 1). 59.1% said they are very satisfied and 31.6% said they are satisfied with the ability of the media used by teachers to support the speed of the communication process and access to learning information (see point 2). In terms of the teacher's willingness to listen students and address student complaints regarding the learning media used, most students are very satisfied with the services provided by the teacher in listening, overcoming and providing solutions to students' difficulties in using or accessing online learning media during the Covid-19 pandemic. (see points 3,4 and 5).

Table 3.
Belief Satisfaction Assessment of Online Learning Systems during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Items	*VDS (%)	*DS (%)	*S (%)	*VS	Mean
1. Teacher knowledge in using media in online learning.	6.9	17.5	26.3	49.4	3.18
2. The teacher hospitality during learning communication in online learning media.	8.4	16.3	16.9	58.4	3.25
3. The teachers' attention given in assisting students during using the media.	5.3	12.2	32.2	50.3	3.28
4. Student satisfaction with convenience in using online learning media.	9.4	16.3	25.9	48.4	3.13
5. The learning media reputation by teachers during online learning.	3.4	11.3	26.3	59.1	3.41
6. The internet data saving features satisfaction during online learning applications used.	3.4	8.8	29.4	58.4	3.43

*VDS: Very Dissatisfied, DS: Dissatisfied, S: Satisfied, VS: Very Satisfied.

Based on table 3, this study found that the dimension of belief satisfaction, student satisfaction with the ability of teachers to create and increase students' confidence and trust during online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. Based on the survey conducted, the students are very satisfied with the teachers' knowledge of using online learning media so students are more comfortable when their teachers understood technically the use of online learning media (49.4 stated 'very satisfactory' and 26.3% stated 'satisfactory'). In addition, in terms of learning services during a pandemic, students stated that they are very satisfied with the services of teachers during online learning, they stated that they are very satisfied (58.4%) with the teachers hospitality, attention (50.3% stated that they are very satisfied and 32.2% said they are satisfied), and comfort (48.4% said they are very satisfied and 25.9% said they are satisfied). In terms of the quality of the online learning media used by teachers, 59.1% of students in Madiun Regency stated that they are 'very satisfied' with the reputation of the learning media used by teachers and 26.3% stated that they are 'satisfied'. For the internet data saving feature of applications used in online learning,

58.4% of students stated that they are very satisfied and 29.4% said they are satisfied with this feature.

Table 4.
Evaluation of Empathy Satisfaction with Online Learning Systems during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Items	*VDS (%)	*DS (%)	*S (%)	*VS	Mean
1. The ease of accessing media used in online learning.	0.3	5.3	8.1	86.3	3.80
2. The ability of the media used to facilitate communication between teachers and students.	3.8	10.6	13.4	72.2	3.54
3. The teacher's ability to understand students' desires for media use.	3.1	18.8	13.8	64.4	3.39
4. Teachers' efforts to improve media deficiencies in online learning.	8.1	22.2	30.9	38.8	3.00
5. Teachers' hospitality during online learning.	12.2	30.3	23.1	34.4	2.80
6. The attention given to students by teachers during online learning	8.1	32.5	21.6	37.8	2.89
7. Teacher efforts in overcoming obstacles to the use of online learning media.	8.8	36.6	2.8	25.9	2.72
8. Willingness of teachers to help students who experience difficulties in online learning	12.2	27.8	31.3	28.8	2.77
9. The teacher's willingness to receive input from students regarding obstacles in the use of online learning media	7.5	26.3	20.0	46.3	3.05

*VDS: Very Dissatisfied, DS: Dissatisfied, S: Satisfied, VS: Very Satisfied.

The next analysis is an empathy satisfaction analysis. This satisfaction refers to the willingness of teachers and the school to pay special attention to students by trying to understand students' desires for the use of media in online learning. Based on the table above, this study found a tendency that on average students in grades (7) seventh and 8 (eight) of junior high schools in the Madiun Regency area are satisfied with this service. The majority of respondents stated that they are very satisfied with the convenience provided by online learning media in terms of accessibility (86.3% stated 'very satisfied') and the interaction between teachers and students (72.2% stated 'very satisfied'). Beside that mostly respondents also satisfied with the ability of teachers to understand students' desires in terms of using instructional media. In addition, this study also found that in the service dimension of the teachers, on average students are satisfied with the services provided by the teachers, such as the teacher hospitality when teaching in online media, correcting deficiencies in the media used in online learning, paying attention to students. during learning, the teacher's

efforts to overcome communication barriers or the use of media in online learning media, the willingness of teachers to help difficulties in online learning and the willingness of teachers to receive input from students regarding obstacles during online learning (see table 4.).

Then, on the aspect of tangible satisfaction, this study found that the average respondent was satisfied with the features, services and materials provided by the school and online learning media. 51.3% of respondents said that they are satisfied with the appearance of the learning media selected and used by teachers in online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic, another 17.2% said 'very satisfied'. Regarding the quality of communication made by teachers during the online teaching and learning process, respondents stated that they are very satisfied (40.3%) and satisfied (35%) with the quality of teachers' communication during online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. In addition, smooth internet access during online learning makes students feel satisfied with the services provided by the school (see table 5).

Table 5.
Tangible Satisfaction Assessment of Online Learning Systems during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Items	*VDS (%)	*DS (%)	*S (%)	*VS	Mean
1. Display of learning media used by teachers during online learning.	4.1	27.5	51.3	17.2	2.82
2. Communication facilities that exist in online learning media.	13.1	36.3	29.1	21.6	2.59
3. The teacher communication during online learning.	6.9	17.8	35.0	40.3	3.09
4. Smooth internet access in online teaching and learning process during the Covid-19 pandemic.	10.3	30.0	36.3	23.1	2.73
5. Teachers' hospitality during online learning.	7.5	26.3	20.0	46.3	3.05

*VDS: Very Dissatisfied, DS: Dissatisfied, S: Satisfied, VS: Very Satisfied.

Based on the results of the analysis of the frequency distribution of student satisfaction with online learning media during the Covid-19 pandemic, it can be said that there seems to be a tendency for junior high school students, especially students with educational backgrounds of grades VII (seven) and VIII (eight) to feel very satisfied with the use of online learning media during the corona virus outbreak. The ease of accessing learning knowledge and information makes students feel satisfied with this learning process. In addition, the services provided both by the media (cheap, easy to access and easy to use) are also supported by the services of teachers and the school in serving, guiding and directing students when they experience problems or obstacles in using learning media, making students feel very comfortable. satisfied with learning media although students face with health crisis caused by the Covid-19 virus.

Relationship between perceptions and expectations of learning media and satisfaction in online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic

The next analysis is to test the extent of the relationship between students' expectations of online learning media and the satisfaction they get. Using Pearson's correlational analysis, this study found

that there is a positive and significant relationship between expectations and satisfaction generated in online learning. Expectations for the ability of the media to support the online learning process during a pandemic, features that can facilitate the online learning process, the willingness of teachers and schools to assist students in the process of using online learning media, the ability of teachers to master learning media technology, and the willingness of educators to giving special attention to students during the teaching and learning process, has a positive and significant relationship to the satisfaction they expect (see table 6).

Table 6.
The relationship between the satisfaction sought and the satisfaction received
in the use of online learning media

The satisfaction sought (gratification sought) in online learning media.	Satisfaction obtained from the use of online learning media	
	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-Tailed)
1. Reliability expectations (reliability)	.371	.000
2. Responsiveness expectations (responsive)	.313	.000
3. Faith Hope (Assurance)	.343	.000
4. Empathy Hope (Emphaty)	.241	.000
5. Tangiable hope (Tangiabile)	.234	.000

Based on the results of the correlation analysis conducted, the study found that all the satisfaction sought or expected by junior high school students in Madiun Regency had a positive and significant relationship to the satisfaction they obtained from using online learning media during the Covid-19 virus pandemic. The degree of relationship obtained, reliability expectations, responsiveness and confidence expectations have an adequate correlation with satisfaction with the use of online learning media. Meanwhile, empathic expectations and tangible expectations have a weak correlation with the satisfaction of using online learning media among students in grades VII and VIII of Madiun Regency.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the survey analysis conducted, it can be said that in times of uncertainty due to the Covid-19 virus that has hit the whole world and has significantly affected the way people live, especially in the aspect of education. Online learning media is an effective learning strategy so the teaching and learning process continues during the pandemic. Based on the results of the analysis, this study found that students, especially students in junior high schools in the Madiun Regency area, very satisfied with the use of internet-connected digital media. Student satisfaction is not only limited to technical aspects such as the ease of communication, the ease of accessing learning information, and the ease of teaching and learning. But also non-technical satisfaction such as the ability of the teachers to guide and provide directions to students in using online learning media, the willingness of teachers to listen, overcome and provide solutions to problems faced by students in the online learning process during the Covid-19 pandemic.

The next analysis is to examine the relationship between the satisfaction expectations sought by students and the satisfaction they get from using online learning media. By using Pearson product moment relational analysis, this study found that the satisfaction expectations that students seek in

using online learning media have a positive and significant relationship to the satisfaction they get from using these learning media, even though the degree of satisfaction produced varies. Reliability satisfaction expectations, responsiveness and confidence expectations have a sufficient correlation with satisfaction with the use of online learning media. Meanwhile, empathy expectations and tangible expectations have a weak correlation with the satisfaction of using online learning media. From the findings of this study, it is hoped that it can be used to determine the possibility of differences in the perception of media quality by students with the satisfaction obtained by students so that the findings from this research can be used as material for consideration by stakeholders in the field of education, especially teachers and schools so that it is known which aspects need to be improved. in order to meet the satisfaction or needs of students in learning through online digital media.

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